

Textual analysis of the WGI contribution to the AR6:

Review of the use of uncertainty language and scenarios in the report chapters, ES, TS & SPM

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Written by Chavelli, F. and Connors, S. L.

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Introduction

The aim of this study is to quantify and qualify the use of uncertainty language and different evolution scenarios in the WGI contribution to the AR6, *Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis*.

The uncertainty language corresponds to the use of calibrated IPCC language to describe the probability, agreement, quantity and quality of evidence, and the degree of confidence in the assertions. The scenarios studied are the RCPs (Representative Concentration Pathway) and SSPs (Shared Socioeconomic Pathways).

The use of these different terms has been discussed in the report chapters as well as in the Executive Summaries (ES), the Technical Summary (TS) and the Summary for Policy Maker (SPM).

For each of the terms (uncertainty language or evolution scenario), a quantitative study shows the number of terms used within the chapters. A standardized version is sometimes presented to qualify the influence of the length of the chapters. A qualitative study then compares the distribution of terms across the chapters and tries to explain the observations. A similar study is then conducted to compare the full report with the TS and the SPM.

The terms searched in the report were only in lower case (e.g. "very likely" and not "Very likely") in order to count only occurrences within sentences and to limit the contribution of terms in table headings for example.

1. Uncertainty language across the chapters

A. Likelihood

The likelihood of the events quoted in the report are quantified by a **likelihood term**. The table below presents the IPCC calibrated language with the probability associated with each of these terms. For the sake of simplicity and visualization, some terms that are very rarely used (e.g. *extremely likely, as likely as not, exceptionally unlikely*) are attached to the closest terms in **groups of terms**.

Group of Terms	Term	Likelihood of the outcome
Virtually certain	Virtually certain	99-100% probability
	Extremely likely	95-100% probability
Very likely	Very likely	90-100% probability
Likely	Likely	66-100% probability
	More likely than not	50-100% probability
Unlikely	About as likely as not	33 to 66% probability
	Unlikely	0-33% probability
	Very unlikely	0-10% probability
	Exceptionally unlikely	0-1% probability

Table 1 : Likelihood terms definitions and groups

The use of groups of terms is motivated by the under-representation of some likelihood terms. The graph on the left showing the occurrences of each term can be compared with the one on the right dealing with the terms grouped. The details of the values are given in the appendix.ⁱ

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A.1 Occurrence

The distribution of these likelihood terms is given by chapter in the graph below.

Figure 1 : Likelihood terms occurrences in chapters

It can be seen that the distribution of terms is very uneven in the chapters. Atlas, Chapter 4 and Chapter 9 account for almost 40% of the occurrences. Conversely, chapters 5, 6 and 10 represent less than 10% of it.

The graph below is normalised by chapter size (percentage of likelihood terms among the words in the chapter) and allows to appreciate the relative quantity of likelihood terms in the chapters. It nuances the share of uncertainty language in Chapter 9 but confirms it in the case of Chapter 4, the latter being dedicated to future climate and scenarios.

Figure 2 : Likelihood terms proportion in the chapters

A.2 Diversity

The following graphs detail these values by distinguishing the different likelihood terms according to the groups defined in Table 1. The graph on the left shows the occurrences while the graph on the right shows the proportion of each group within the chapters.

Figure 3: Likelihood terms occurrences in the chapters

Figure 4: Likelihood terms proportion in the chapters

Thus, in each chapter there is a large proportion (nearly 80% on average) of the *likely* and *very likely* groups (two intermediate shades of blue) while the *virtually certain* and *unlikely* groups (dark blue and light blue) are much less represented (respectively 15% and 5% on average). Looking at the proportions, it can be seen that the chapters have broadly the same distribution of likelihood of terms.

A.3 Comparison with ES

The use of likelihood terms in the Executive Summaries is presented in the graph below. It appears that the distribution of terms, both qualitatively and quantitatively, reflects that of the chapters (Figure 3).

Figure 5: Likelihood terms occurrences in Executive Summaries

A.4 Conclusion

Quantitatively, the chapters use a highly variable number of likelihood terms. Qualitatively, the chapters present a fairly similar distribution, which is not uniform in the use of terms : *likely* and *very likely* are the most used.

B. Confidence

Confidence terms are used with five qualifiers: *very low*, *low*, *medium*, *high* and *very high*. If confidence cannot be used, then only evidence and agreement are used, as shown in the following table. Confidence increases towards the top-right corner as suggested by the increasing strength of shading.

Figure 6 : A depiction of evidence and agreement statements and their relationship to confidence.

B.1 Occurrence

The distribution of the confidence terms in the chapter in the graph below.

Figure 7 : Confidence terms occurrences in the chapters

It can be noted that the amount of confidence terms is unevenly distributed across chapters. Chapter 12 (dedicated to information for regional impact and for risk assessment) contains nearly one in five terms in the report. Chapter 1 on the other hand contains less than 3%.

This distribution varies only slightly when relating the quantity of terms to the size of the chapters as shown in the graph below.

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Figure 8 : Confidence terms proportion in the chapters

B.2 Diversity

The diversity of the confidence terms used is detailed in the graphs below.

Figure 9: Confidence terms occurrences in the chapters

Figure 10: Confidence terms proportion in the chapters

A fairly similar distribution can be seen for the chapters: almost half of the terms used (on average) are *high confidence*, about one third are *medium confidence*. There are less *very high confidence* and *low confidence* (respectively 5% and 15% on average). The term *very low confidence* is hardly used.

B.3 Comparison with ES

The use of confidence terms in the Executive Summaries is presented in the graph below. There are quantitative differences with the distribution observed in the chapters (Figure 9), especially for the Atlas and Chapter 12. The terms used, however, seem to be used in the same proportions.

Figure 11 : Confidence terms occurrences in Executive Summaries

B.4 Relationship with evidence and agreement

The table below shows the number of evidence and agreement terms cited together in the chapters (which is not systematic). It can be seen that limited and robust levels of evidence are generally associated with low and high agreement respectively.

		Evidence		
		Limited	Medium	Robust
Agreement	High	15	20	46
	Medium	20	6	10
	Low	20	6	0

Table 2 : Relationship between evidence and agreement

Conclusion

A similar conclusion to that of the likelihood terms can be made. Quantitatively, the chapters use a highly variable number of likelihood terms. Qualitatively, the chapters present a fairly similar distribution, which is not uniform in the use of terms (*high confidence* and *medium confidence* are the most used).

C. Evidence & agreement

The type, quantity, quality and consistency of evidence is expressed through **evidence terms**. These terms are complimented by the **agreement terms** allowing to quantify the consensus on a given assertion.

C.1 Occurrence

The number of evidence and agreement terms are of the same order of magnitude (330 and 259 respectively) in the chapters. In the graph below, it can be seen that the amount of terms used varies greatly from one chapter to another (regardless of their size). However, the number of evidence terms (dark blue) seems similar to the number of agreement terms (light blue) in most chapters. This is to be expected as the IPCC Uncertainty Guidance note recommends to use evidence and agreement together.

Figure 12 : Evidence and agreement terms occurrences in the chapters

C.2 Diversity

Each finding in the report is based on an assessment of the underlying evidence and agreement. Evidence is designated by 3 qualifiers: *robust*, *medium*, *limited*. The agreements are qualified as *high*, *medium* or *low*.

The graphs below present the detailed occurrences of each evidence and agreement term in the chapters.

Figure 13 : Evidence terms occurrences in the chapters

Figure 14: Agreement terms occurrences in the chapters

It appears that the variety (as well as the quantity) of evidence and agreement terms used in the chapters varies greatly. Chapter 12, dedicated to regional impacts and risks, has the most terms of evidence, and in particular, *limited evidence*. Chapter 5, on global carbon and other biogeochemical cycles and feedbacks uses the most agreement terms, and in particular *high agreement*.

Finally, it seems that for some chapters (e.g. Chapters 5 to 10) the proportions of *robust*, *medium* and *limited evidence* are respectively quite close to those of *high*, *medium* and *low agreement*. It is not indicated, however, that these qualifiers are used together to describe the same assertion.

The Executive Summaries do not contain sufficient evidence and agreement to make a comparison.

Conclusion

Both quantitatively and qualitatively, the chapters are very different in their use of evidence and agreement terms. However, it seems that the levels of evidence and agreement are often linked.

Conclusion

The following table shows the relative number of terms used in each chapter. The quantities associated with the terms evidence and agreement are similar. It appears that chapters 1 and 6 use fewer of the terms studied (in general), while chapters 9 and 12 use more.

	Atlas	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Likelihood	High	Medium	Medium	Medium	High	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium	High	Medium	Medium	Medium
Confidence	Medium	High	High	Medium	Medium	High							
Evidence, agreement	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium	High	Medium	Medium	Medium	High	High	Medium	High

Amount of terms	High	Medium	Low
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2. Uncertainty language across ES, TS, SPM versus Chapters

This section looks at the use of uncertainty language in the various reports. The associated data is given in the appendix.ⁱⁱ The Executive Summary, presented as a report, correspond to the concatenation of the chapter ES.

A. Likelihood

The graph on the left shows the (relative) amount of likelihood terms in the reports, while the graph on the right shows the diversity of terms used in the reports.

Figure 15: Likelihood terms proportion in reports

Figure 16: Likelihood terms proportion in reports

It can be noticed that the ES, TS and SPM use far more likelihood terms (relatively to their size) than the full report. The use of terms is uneven but almost identical in the four reports.

B. Confidence

In the case of confidence terms, the ES, TS and SPM use many more terms than the full report. The three quantifiers are used in similar proportions in the four reports with a majority of *high confidence* and *medium confidence*. *Very low confidence* on the other hand is used very little in the full report and not at all in the TS and SPM.

Figure 17: Confidence terms proportion in reports

Figure 18: Confidence terms proportion in reports

C. Evidence

In the case of the evidence terms, the same trend can be observed quantitatively, with a smaller difference between the full report and the other reports. On the other hand, the use of the terms is very varied: the ES and TS does not use medium evidence and the SPM uses only limited evidence.

Figure 19: Evidence terms proportion in reports

Figure 20: Evidence terms proportion in reports

D. Agreement

In the case of agreement terms, more occurrences appear in the ES than in the report, TS or SPM. The three quantifiers are used in similar proportions in the TS and ES. The SPM does not use *high agreement*.

Figure 21: Agreement terms proportion in reports

Figure 22: Agreement terms proportion in reports

Conclusion

The reports have a very different use of uncertainty terms, summarised in the table below. With the exception of agreement terms, the full report uses (relatively) fewer terms than the TS and SPM. The SPM uses the most likelihood and evidence terms, while the TS uses the most confidence terms.

	Full Report	ES	TS	SPM
Likelihood	Low	Medium	Medium	Medium
Confidence	Low	Medium	Medium	Medium
Evidence	Low	Medium	Medium	Medium
Agreement	High	High	Medium	Medium

Amount of terms	High	Medium	Low
-----------------	------	--------	-----

The distribution of these terms is not balanced for any of the terms but similar in the ratios for the likelihood and confidence terms. The proportion used for evidence and agreement terms in TS and SPM must be qualified by the very low number of occurrences (see appendix).

3. SSP & RCP scenarios

The RCP scenarios are four radiative forcing trajectory scenarios to the year 2300. The SSP scenarios are trajectories developed to complement the RPCs with various socio-economic adaptation and mitigation issues. They can be designated in the reports by their value (e.g. SSP1-1.9) or by a description (e.g. very low emission scenario).¹

A. SSP & RCP scenarios across the chapters

A.1 Occurrence

The distributions of SSP & RCP scenarios by chapter are given in the graphs below.

Figure 23: SSP occurrences in the chapters

Figure 24: RCP occurrences in the chapters

Dealing with SSP scenarios, Chapter 4 (dedicated to future climate and scenarios) contains as expected far more SSP scenarios than the other chapters (30% of the total). Other chapters (e.g. 2, 3, 7) contain only about ten occurrences. The distribution of RCP scenarios is also uneven, with Chapter 12 accounting for 40% of the report's occurrences, compared to less than 2% for Chapters 2, 3, 6 and 7 together. These proportions remain the same when normalized by chapter size.

¹ The expressions searched for are detailed in the table below.

SSP1-1.9	'very low emission scenario', 'very low-emission scenario', 'very low and low GHG emissions', 'very low or low GHG emissions'
SSP1-2.6	'low emission scenario', 'low-emission scenario', 'very low and low GHG emissions'
SSP3-7.0	'high emission scenario', 'high-emission scenario', 'high and very high GHG emissions', 'high or very high GHG emissions'
SSP5-8.5	'very high emission scenario', 'very high-emission scenario', 'high and very high GHG emissions', 'high or very high GHG emissions'

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A.2 Diversity

The graphs below show the proportion that each SSP & RCP scenario represents within the chapters.

Figure 25: SSP proportion in the chapters

Figure 26: RCP proportion in the chapters

The distribution of the SSP & RCP scenarios within the chapters is very variable. With the exception of Chapter 3, it appears that among the five SSP scenarios, SSP1-1.9 is underrepresented in most chapters (representing less than 20% of the scenarios cited), while SSP5-8.5 is often overrepresented (representing more than 20% of the scenarios cited). Regarding RCP scenarios, RCP8.5 accounts for more than half of the scenarios cited in most chapters.

A.3 Comparison with ES

The use of SSP & RCP scenarios in the Executive Summaries are presented in the graphs below. It appears that for most chapters, the distribution of SSP scenarios, both qualitatively and quantitatively, reflects that of the chapters (Figure 25). In the case of RCP scenarios, only the chapters citing the most RCP scenarios (Figure 26) contain some in their ES.

A.4 Details in chapters

The following table shows the detailed values for the different SSPs scenarios by chapter, Chapter 0 corresponding to the Atlas.

Occurrences for SSP in chapters

Chapter 0	42	15	15	30	0
Chapter 1	35	25	14	20	26
Chapter 2	5	1	5	3	2
Chapter 3	0	0	7	0	0
Chapter 4	106	119	42	110	49
Chapter 5	18	4	3	20	1
Chapter 6	30	76	10	26	20
Chapter 7	2	1	1	3	2
Chapter 8	39	10	23	15	11
Chapter 9	104	16	26	77	11
Chapter 10	17	2	2	4	0
Chapter 11	6	8	5	6	6
Chapter 12	68	4	14	51	2
	SSP5-8.5	SSP3-7.0	SSP2-4.5	SSP1-2.6	SSP1-1.9

Figure 27 : Occurrences for SSP in chapters

B. SSP & RCP scenarios across the SPM and TS versus Chapters

B.1 Occurrence

The graphs below show the number of SSP & RCP scenarios cited in each report.

Figure 28: SSP proportion in the chapters

Figure 29: RCP proportion in the chapters

It appears that the SSP scenarios are more frequently cited than the RCP scenarios in all reports. The ES and TS uses more SSP scenarios than the full report but less RCP scenarios. The SPM has the most important use of SSP scenarios but does not cite any RCP scenarios.

B.2 Diversity

The distribution of each SSP & RCP scenario in the reports is given below.

Figure 30: SSP proportion in the reports

Figure 31: RCP proportion in the reports

The use of SSP scenarios across the reports is fairly balanced, especially in the SPM. In contrast, both the full report and the TS have a disproportionate use of the RCP8.5 scenario compared to the other RCP scenarios.

4. Comparison with previous SPMs

The use of uncertainty language in previous SPMs is presented in the graphs below.

Figure 32 : Likelihood terms use in SPMs

Figure 33 : Confidence terms use in SPMs

The terms for evidence and agreement are used only (or almost only) in the AR6. Only the SPM in AR5 uses RCP scenarios, and only AR6 mentions SSP scenarios.

The use of the word "will" in the different SPMs is shown in the graph below.

Figure 34 : Use of "will" in SPMs

Conclusion

The table below summarises the results obtained. It represents for each report and each term studied, the quantity of terms used and their distribution (balanced : the different terms are used in similar proportions or unbalanced : some terms are used more than others).

	Report	ES	TS	SPM
Likelihood	-	-	-	-
Evidence	-	-	-	-
Agreement	+	-	+	-
Confidence	-	-	-	-
SSP scenarios	+	+	+	+
RCP scenarios	-	-	-	

Quantity		Balance	
High		Balanced	+
Intermediate		Unbalanced	-
Low		N/A	

Table 3 : Summary of results

The relative amount of uncertainty language and scenario terms used differs in each report. However, it appears that the SPM and the ES use more uncertainty language and SSP scenarios than the report or the TS.

With the exception of the agreement terms in the report and in the TS, the distribution of the uncertainty terms is not balanced in the reports, some terms being used more than others. The terms used in majority among likelihood, evidence and confidence language are respectively *likely* and *very likely*, *limited evidence*, *high confidence* and *medium confidence*. However, the use of SSP scenarios is well balanced across the reports.

Appendix

ⁱ Details of the use of likelihood terms in the chapters are given below.

	Virtually certain		Very likely	Likely		Unlikely					Total
	virtually certain	extremely likely	very likely	likely	more likely than not	as likely as not	unlikely	very unlikely	extremely unlikely	exceptionally unlikely	
Atlas	18	0	64	93	0	0	1	1	0	0	177
1	7	5	25	42	2	1	3	5	1	1	92
2	16	3	61	56	5	1	4	0	0	0	146
3	12	12	49	45	0	0	1	0	0	0	119
4	14	1	79	112	10	1	9	4	4	0	234
5	8	0	14	17	0	0	2	5	0	0	46
6	0	2	19	19	0	0	4	0	0	0	44
7	9	4	71	56	1	0	2	3	2	0	148
8	8	2	40	52	2	1	2	0	0	0	107
9	18	4	59	140	0	1	3	2	0	0	227
10	8	1	7	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	29
11	16	5	41	55	3	0	2	1	4	0	127
12	39	4	54	43	1	0	2	0	0	0	143
Total	173	43	583	743	24	5	35	21	11	1	1639

ⁱⁱ Occurrences for different uncertainty language terms in TS and SPM are given below.

Likelihood	virtually certain	extremely likely	very likely	likely	more likely than not	as likely as not	unlikely	very unlikely	extremely unlikely	exceptionally unlikely	Total
TS	44	13	99	127	6	0	3	5	5	0	302
SPM	11	5	38	54	5	1	2	2	3	1	122

Confidence	very high confidence	high confidence	medium confidence	low confidence	very low confidence	Total
TS	37	396	274	58	0	765
SPM	10	102	58	10	0	180

Evidence	robust evidence	medium evidence	limited evidence	Total
TS	11	0	8	19
SPM	0	0	7	7

Agreement	high agreement	medium agreement	low agreement	Total
TS	1	3	2	6
SPM	0	1	1	2